

Image Recognition with Machine Learning

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Abstract—We present image recognition using a classical machine learning algorithm, specifically Support Vector Machines (SVM), and show an image library of faces of recent U.S. presidents. We demonstrate that even with a limited number of samples—on the order of hundreds—good results can be obtained without deep learning, and very good results can be achieved if the number of samples is higher, on the order of thousands.

Index Terms—machine learning, support vector machine, gradient boosting, image library, HOG, face recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

We present an image library created by crawling images on the internet and then using a portion of the library to build a model for image classification, using a different portion to test how well the model performs, and reporting the results of the classification model’s performance.

The novel feature of this study is demonstrating that good results can be obtained with just a few hundred images, and very good results can be achieved if the dataset size is in the thousands. We show that it is not necessary to use millions of images or incur the cost of training deep learning models to achieve acceptable results for face classification tasks.

II. TASKS

The study was divided into the tasks outlined in Table ?? . The rest of this paper describes how the dataset was created and used as input to train a machine learning model, how the model was trained, the testing of the model, and the results.

TABLE I
PROJECT TASKS

Step	Task
1	Collect 1000+ images from the internet; images of U.S. presidents; place in an Image Library on Dropbox
2	Convert Image Library to a dataset for input into the machine learning program
3	Split the dataset into training and testing portions; no image should be in both
4	Train the model using the training portion
5	Test the model using the testing portion
6	Examine the performance of the model
7	Prepare project report
8	Create and record a group video presentation

III. DATASET CREATION

A. Image Count

The dataset was created by crawling the Google and Bing web search engines. Approximately 40 to 100 images of each U.S. president were collected. We focused on recent presidents, as a large number of photographs are available for them. Table ?? shows the image set sizes.

TABLE II
IMAGE COUNT PER PRESIDENT

No.	President	Count
41	George Bush	114
42	William J. Clinton	44
43	George W. Bush	72
44	Barack H. Obama	102
45	Donald J. Trump	135
46	Joseph R. Biden, Jr.	32

B. Image Library

The initial image library consisted of files of different types including JPG, JPEG, PNG, GIF, and WEBP. To feed the images into our machine learning program, the images needed to be of a single type. We chose JPG (which includes JPEG). A Python utility was written to convert PNG and GIF files in the dataset to JPG using Pillow (a derivative of PIL). One by one, this utility converts each PNG or GIF file to JPG and saves them accordingly. The WEBP files were converted manually.

C. Pre-Processing

The dataset was allocated 80% to the training set and 20% to the testing set. This division was performed using the `train_test_split` utility in `scikit-learn`, with `shuffle` set to `TRUE` and `random state` set to 42. Table ?? shows the distribution of images by president.

TABLE III
TRAIN/TEST SPLIT

#	President	Total	Train	Test
41	George Bush	74	59	15
42	William J. Clinton	27	21	6
43	George W. Bush	53	42	11
44	Barack H. Obama	67	53	14
45	Donald J. Trump	71	56	15
46	Joseph R. Biden, Jr.	27	21	6

Fig. 1. Distribution of images per president in the dataset.

IV. FEATURE SELECTION

Features are attributes or properties of the data selected for representation in the model. Data may have many features—for example, the Iris dataset has four features (sepal length, sepal width, petal length, petal width)—but not all features are relevant for the recognition task.

Similarly, we need to find characteristics of presidential face images that provide unique, distinguishing information useful for identification. Classical image recognition employs the following types of features [?]:

- Haar-like features
- Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)
- Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT)
- Speeded Up Robust Feature (SURF)

One effective method for capturing facial characteristics is the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG). HOG finds the gradient orientation in localized portions of an image: it examines sections of lines and curves, draws gradients at most points, and then uses the angle of each gradient as a representation. A flat line will have a gradient of zero, while a curve will have a positive gradient angle. Areas of images with identifiable features—nose, mouth, eyes—will have distinct numeric gradients, and these values will be similar for the same person since they share the same facial structure. Fig. ?? shows the HOG representation for President Biden’s image.

Fig. 2. Original image and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) for President Biden.

V. MODEL & ALGORITHM

In machine learning, the algorithm is called a model, as it models the phenomenon and attempts to output results given input, in the same way a real-world system would. The next

challenge was to find a suitable modeling algorithm. We found from research that Support Vector Machines (SVM) work well for HOG features. In addition, we used Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), K-Nearest Neighbors, Decision Trees, and Random Forest models. We created a scikit-learn pipeline that applies all models sequentially and selects the best-performing one.

We also considered two additional techniques—deep learning and transfer learning—but dismissed both. Table ?? summarizes the comparison between traditional image processing and deep learning.

TABLE IV
TRADITIONAL IMAGE PROCESSING VS. DEEP LEARNING [?]

Criterion	Traditional	Deep Learning
Training dataset	Small	Large
Computing power	Low	High
Feature engineering	Required	Unnecessary
Training time	Short	Long
Annotation time	Short	Long
Algorithm transparency	High	Low
Domain expertise	High	Low
Priors (Assumptions)	Few	Many
Proprietary risk	DLLs (Low)	Models, DLLs (High)
Deployment flexibility	High	Low
Expenditure (BOM)	Low	High

Deep learning would require many more images—hundreds of thousands—and it is not easy to find that many images for all presidents. Additionally, deep learning would require significant hardware resources (GPUs), increasing the cost of the study.

VI. TRANSFER LEARNING

Transfer learning was considered but ultimately discarded, as we wanted to test actual model building from scratch. Transfer learning refers to a technique in which a model trained on different images is used to create embeddings for the images at hand. The idea is that a model trained on millions of general faces will have a vector space representation of facial features (nose, hair, etc.), and creating a vector embedding of a president’s face will yield a unique representation suitable for recognition. Pre-built models such as FaceNet and DeepFace are available through libraries like `face-recognition` and `dlib`. However, we chose not to use transfer learning, as the purpose of this project was to train our own model.

VII. PARAMETER SEARCH

Each of the above-mentioned models has hyperparameters that can be tuned to improve performance. We used the Grid Search method to provide the pipeline with a grid of parameters to try and select the best-performing model and parameter combination. We used the `GridSearchCV` class with 10-fold cross-validation. Cross-validation divides the dataset into multiple subsets with one holdout set; the model is trained on some subsets and tested on the holdout. Listing ?? shows the grid search configuration.

Fig. 3. Transfer Learning and Euclidean distance between face embeddings for identification.

```

grid_search = GridSearchCV(
    HOG_pipeline,
    param_grid,
    cv=10,
    n_jobs=-1,
    scoring="accuracy",
    verbose=0,
    return_train_score=True,
)
grid_res = grid_search.fit(X_train, y_train)

```

Listing 1. Grid search configuration.

The library of choice for machine learning models is scikit-learn [?], the industry standard for non-deep-learning use cases. It provides excellent APIs and helper functions for loading data, working with DataFrames, and integrating with pandas and NumPy. For plotting, we used matplotlib; for image processing, we used scikit-image and the Python Image Library (Pillow). Table ?? lists the important libraries used.

TABLE V
LIBRARIES USED

Name	Description
scikit-learn	ML Models
scikit-image	Image utilities
pandas, NumPy	DataFrame manipulation
matplotlib	Plots
Pillow	Image utilities
imageio[pyav]	Image loaders
Keras	Model saving utility

VIII. SCIKIT-LEARN PIPELINE

Scikit-learn offers an abstraction called Pipeline that connects different processing steps into a single sequence, making it easy to apply the full workflow to multiple records. We created a pipeline with four steps, as shown in Table ??.

Listing ?? shows the pipeline definition.

```

HOG_pipeline = Pipeline(
    [
        ("grayify", RGB2GrayTransformer()),
        (
            "hogify",
            HogTransformer(

```

TABLE VI
PIPELINE COMPONENTS

Name	Description
RGB2GrayTransformer	RGB to grayscale conversion
HogTransformer	Extract HOG features
StandardScaler	Normalize features to 0–1 range
SGDClassifier	Stochastic Gradient Descent model
SVC	Support Vector Classifier model
MiniBatchKMeans	KMeans model

```

pixels_per_cell=(14, 14),
cells_per_block=(2, 2),
orientations=9,
block_norm="L2-Hys",
),
),
("scalify", StandardScaler()),
("classify", SGDClassifier(
    random_state=42,
    max_iter=1000,
    tol=1e-3,
    verbose=0)),
]
)

```

Listing 2. Scikit-learn pipeline definition.

IX. DATA PRE-PROCESSING

The images obtained from the internet are in RGB color and of varying sizes. All images need to be of the same size and shape for use with the scikit-learn API. Additionally, it is easier to process grayscale images since color is not a relevant feature. Since images may contain redundant background elements, we need to crop each image to contain only the face. Finally, all grayscale pixel values should be normalized to lie between 0 and 1 so that all features are in the same range. The pre-processing pipeline is as follows:

- 1) **Face Crop:** Extract the face region from the image.
- 2) **Resize:** Resize all images to 200×200 pixels.
- 3) **Grayscale:** Convert from RGB to grayscale.
- 4) **Standardize:** Normalize pixel values to the range $[0, 1]$.

X. TRAINING

Training was performed on personal laptops with a 2.6 GHz Dual-Core Intel i5 processor and 8 GB RAM. Training took approximately 2 hours for images of five presidents. The majority of time was spent on parameter grid search and model training. Fig. ?? shows one instance of the training process.

XI. TESTING MODEL

The testing data produced approximately 70% average accuracy. This result was obtained using grid search only on the HOG parameters and not on the other model parameters, due to time constraints. The best accuracy score achieved was 76%. This 70–76% range was obtained on the subset of the dataset consisting of recent presidents with a larger number of pictures. For presidents from the 18th and 19th centuries, the images were not of good quality and were mostly paintings, resulting in an overall score of approximately 56%. The best

```

Norm: 2464.15, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1797.320629, T: 1521, Avg. loss: 2.780709
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 10
Norm: 2317.18, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 1690, Avg. loss: 1.590486
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 11
Norm: 2180.16, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 1859, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 12
Norm: 2058.44, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 2028, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 13
Norm: 1949.59, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 2197, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 14
Norm: 1851.68, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 2366, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.01 seconds.
-- Epoch 15
Norm: 1763.13, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 2535, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.02 seconds.
-- Epoch 16
Norm: 1682.66, NNZs: 3456, Bias: -1801.252992, T: 2704, Avg. loss: 0.000000
Total training time: 0.02 seconds.

```

Fig. 4. Training console output showing epoch progress, norms, bias, and loss values.

model was Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD). Listing ?? shows the best model configuration and results.

```

Pipeline(steps=[
  ('grayify', RGB2GrayTransformer()),
  ('hogify', HogTransformer(
    cells_per_block=(6, 6),
    orientations=6,
    pixels_per_cell=(12, 12))),
  ('scalify', StandardScaler()),
  ('classify', SGDClassifier(
    random_state=42))]

# Score: 0.7630769230769231
# Best params:
# hogify__cells_per_block: (6, 6)
# hogify__orientations: 6
# hogify__pixels_per_cell: (12, 12)
# Percentage correct: 70.3125

```

Listing 3. Best model pipeline and results.

XII. RESULTS

Accuracy was used as the scoring metric. Accuracy describes how the model performs across all classes and is useful when all classes are of equal importance. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

where TP is true positives, TN is true negatives, FP is false positives, and FN is false negatives.

A confusion matrix provides a comparison between actual and predicted values and helps visualize whether the model is “confused” in discriminating between classes. The confusion matrix is an $N \times N$ matrix, where N is the number of classes. Fig. ?? shows the confusion matrix of our results.

XIII. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

A. Which Technique to Use

The first challenge was deciding which modeling technique to use. Since the objective was to train the model from scratch, transfer learning was ruled out. Deep learning was ruled out due to insufficient training images. This left standard algorithms: SVM, Stochastic Gradient Descent, and Decision Trees.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix of classification results across six presidents.

B. Selection of ML Library

Scikit-learn [?] is the industry standard for non-deep-learning machine learning projects. It was chosen over PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Java-based libraries.

C. Selection of Model or Algorithm

Rather than manually selecting a single algorithm, we automated the process of choosing the best model using Grid Search. Based on accuracy, SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) was selected among Decision Trees and Support Vector Machines.

D. Selection of Performance Metric

Accuracy was used as the scoring metric—the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions.

E. Standardization of Images

All images needed to be the same size, color space, and value range. We used a tool called auto-crop to resize and crop images to 200×200 pixels containing only faces. Some images missed by the tool were cropped manually. We used `StandardScaler` from scikit-learn to normalize all values to $[0, 1]$ and `rgb2gray` from scikit-image to convert images to grayscale.

F. Model Saving/Loading

We encountered errors saving the model in Python’s pickle format. As an alternative, we stored the model in HDF5 format using Keras model saving functions.

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